

Design of Packaging of Power DMOS Transistor

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A simulation study of the packaging of a power double-diffused metal-oxide-semiconductor (DMOS) transistor is presented. The investigation focuses on refining the design to enhance the device's electrical performance. The simulation findings show that an optimized design can improve the switching speed of the power DMOS transistor. The ribbon-bond source electrode's reduced parasitic inductance and resistance enhance the switching speed of the power DMOS transistor by around 13%.

1. Introduction

Power double-diffused metal-oxide-semiconductor (DMOS) transistors are crucial for power electronics and circuits. Indeed, silicon-based DMOS are preferred power technologies for medium to high-power applications [1, 2]. During the constant development of the devices to boost switching speeds, reduce power losses, and improve thermal management, there is also a requirement for enhancement of the power efficiency of DMOS devices. Die bonding is a crucial technology in the semiconductor industry, ensuring electrical connections between a semiconductor chip and its package. Among the most common bonding methods are wire-bond and ribbon-bond. Wire-bond utilizes fine metal wires to create electrical connections. It is flexible, cost-effective, and allows for various configurations, making it suitable for a wide range of applications. Ribbon-bond uses flat metal ribbons which offer lower electrical resistance and higher current-carrying capacity. However, the disadvantages of ribbon-bond are in higher production complexity and costs.

Simulation and modeling are effective tools for examining and optimizing electronic equipment. Simulation can help identify important parts of a device, reducing manufacturing time and cost throughout development and optimization [3]. Therefore, this paper proposes improvements to the electrical characteristics of power DMOS using 3-D device simulation in COMSOL Multiphysics [4]. Two die bonding methods of DMOS, wire-bond and ribbon-bond, are investigated and contrasted. Simulation results illustrated that the optimum ribbon-bond concept outperforms wire-bond in terms of electrical and switching effectiveness.

2. Structure and Simulation Description

The device undergoing examination is a power DMOS transistor. The transistor is fabricated in a PowerFLAT5x6 package. The device is simulated using the 3-D electromagnetic finite element method (FEM) in COMSOL Multiphysics. Parasitic inductances and resistances of drain, gate, and source electrodes are solved by the Magnetic Field, Current Only module. Finally, the parasitic features of electrodes are added to the circuit model of the power DMOS transistor. Switching speed is evaluated in the LTspice circuit simulator.

3. Simulation Results and Discussion

Three different die bonding methods are investigated and contrasted (Fig. 2). The first and second methods include bonding a semiconductor chip in a container with one or more wires. This approach is commonly utilized due to its low cost and high reliability [5]. On the other hand, the wire-bond technique has a larger parasitic resistance and inductance. The other approach is based on the ribbon-bond concept. The ribbon-bond concept can withstand large currents and low resistance.

Fig. 1 One wire-bond, three wires-bond and ribbon-bond power DMOS.

Table 1 the comparison between parasitic inductance and resistance across three die bonding methods for power DMOS transistors.

	1 wire	3 wires	Ribbon
L_{SOURCE}	1.99 μH	1.49 μH	1.22 μH
L_{DRAIN}	0.135 μH		
L_{GATE}	2.76 μH		
R_{SOURCE}	8.48 $\text{m}\Omega$	3.3 $\text{m}\Omega$	1.55 $\text{m}\Omega$
R_{DRAIN}	0.25 $\text{m}\Omega$		
R_{GATE}	18.2 $\text{m}\Omega$		

Table 1 presents a comparison of the electromagnetic characteristics of the drain, gate, and source electrodes for three die bonding methods. The parasitic inductance L and

resistance R of drain, gate, and source interconnections were analyzed. The highest source of parasitic inductance and resistance has one wire-bond. The ribbon-bond has the lowest values of parasitic inductance and resistance. The reason for this is that ribbon-bond has a wider and flatter geometry compared to wire bonds. It provides a larger surface area for electrical contact. This results in lower parasitic inductance and resistance due to the more efficient path for current flow and reduced loop area. On the other hand, wire-bonds have a round cross-section that increases inductive effects and resistance due to their narrower profile and potentially longer connection paths.

After 3-D electro-magnetic FEM simulation and evaluation of the parasitic properties of electrodes, simulations of switching power DMOS transistors were performed. The time taken to turn on and turn off the drain current I_D was analyzed.

Fig. 2 Transistor switching time response for one wire-bond, three wire-bonds, and ribbon-bond lead to the source electrode.

A smaller value of inductance mainly affects the delay of switching in the transistor. Fig. 2 demonstrates the time response of drain current I_D on switching of input gate voltage V_{GS} for the analyzed power DMOS transistor with different die bonding methods. The one wire-bond structure has the largest delay (~ 23 ns), and the ribbon-bond structure has the smallest (~ 20 ns).

4. Conclusions

We provided a 3-D electro-magnetic simulation to optimize the electrical parameters of a power DMOS transistor. Simulation findings indicate that optimal ribbon-bonding beats wire-bonding in power DMOS transistors. The ribbon-bond source electrode's decreased parasitic inductance and resistance increase the switching speed of the power DMOS transistor by around 13%.

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